

ALIGNMENT OF NANO AND MICRON DIAMETER CARBON FILLERS IN EPOXY VIA ELECTRIC FIELD

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental investigation on the *in-situ* alignment of carbon fillers spanning dual length scales via the application of an external electric field to improve the electrical and mechanical properties of filled epoxy polymers. When subjecting the fillers to an applied alternating current electric field within the un-cured, liquid epoxy resin, it was found that the carbon nanofibers (CNFs) and micron diameter, short, carbon fibres (SCFs) would align along the field direction. These epoxy composites containing the nano and micron diameter scale fibrous fillers exposed to an applied electric field exhibited an increased mode I fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , and DC electrical conductivity along the direction of the field. In comparison to the epoxy composites containing the randomly oriented fillers, the alignment of the SCFs and CNFs, when used separately, resulted in an improvements in the G_{Ic} value of 30% and 27%, respectively. However, the multi-scale reinforced epoxy composites, containing the aligned fillers, exhibited a 16-fold increase in the the G_{Ic} compared to the unmodified epoxy and a 39% improvement over the composite containing the randomly oriented fillers. Several key toughening mechanisms through fractographic analysis were identified. The study reveals that aligning the carbon fillers ranging from the nano and the micron length scale offers a promising route in creating multi-scale reinforced composites with greatly enhanced properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight and high strength fibre reinforced polymer composite materials are used in many industries ranging from the aerospace to the civil engineering sector. However, a long-standing dilemma associated with laminated fibre reinforced epoxy composites are the low through-the-thickness strength and fracture toughness. These often stem from the low mechanical properties of the epoxy matrix; making fibre-reinforced epoxy composites susceptible to matrix cracking and delamination [1-2]. Due to the dielectric nature of the epoxy matrix phase, the low through-the-thickness conductivity of composite structures also makes them vulnerable to lightning strike damage and poor electrostatic discharge [3-4]. Therefore, there is a need to improve the multifunctional properties of epoxy composites or fibre-reinforced polymer composites along the thickness direction.

Carbon nanofillers such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) and carbon nanofibres (CNFs) are promising additives for composite materials [1,3-5]. The incorporation of carbon nanofillers in the polymer matrix can provide composites with improved functional (i.e. sensing and conductivity) [4-9] and mechanical properties [9-17]. Arai et al. [10] reported a 50% and ~150% improvement in the mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy laminates by adding carbon nanofibres. The addition of micron length scale chopped short carbon fibres (SCF) to epoxy composites and fibre reinforced epoxy composites also enhances the fracture toughness [11-12]. In the context of multi-scale reinforced epoxy composites, Zhang et al. [13] reported a greater than additive improvement in the fracture toughness when adding CNFs and SCFs together; in a randomly oriented state.

More recently, there is a keen interest in adapting hierarchical design methodologies from nature within existing engineering structures containing highly ordered and aligned constituents or reinforcements [18]. The difficulties associated with poor dispersion and, particularly, the controlled orientation of fillers has limited the full potential of such carbon materials as toughening agents. The use of electric and/or magnetic fields is a promising technique to align both carbon nano- and micron-scale fibres in pre-cured polymer resin systems [15,16,19-24]. Previous studies by the current authors have reported an additional improvement in the electrical and mechanical properties of epoxy nanocomposites by aligning CNFs and GNPs, separately added to the epoxy polymer, using an electric field or a magnetic field [15,20-23]. However, to the authors' knowledge, no detailed comparative studies have been reported on the effect of alignment of carbon-based fillers with varying length scales (i.e. carbon nanofibers and short carbon fibres) on the electrical and mechanical properties. More importantly, there has been no demonstration of utilising electric field-assisted techniques for the *in-situ* alignment of nano- and micron-scale carbon reinforcements.

The present study reports on the alignment of carbon nanofibers (CNFs) and chopped/milled short carbon fibres (SCFs) in an epoxy polymer using an externally applied alternating current electric field, and its effects on the mode I fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) and electrical conductivity of the resulting nano, micron and multi-scale reinforced composites. The fracture energy of the epoxy reinforced with various contents and combination of SCFs and CNFs was measured using mode I double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. The alternating current electric field was applied normal to the bond surfaces of the DCB samples during curing of the resin. The values of the G_{Ic} and the DC electrical conductivity are compared with the unmodified epoxy.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Chopped short carbon fibres (or SCFs) (T300 Colan Australia) were used in this study as the micron scale reinforcements. The SCFs have an average length and diameter of 720 μm and 7 μm , respectively, after milling. Vapour grown carbon nanofibres (Pyrograf®, grade PR-24-XT-HHT) were

used as the nano-reinforcement, having an average length of 20 μm and diameter of 135 nm. Epoxy matrix was manufactured from a two-part system (i.e. resin (105) and slow hardener (206)) supplied by WEST SYSTEM®. Two composite laminates configurations were manufactured containing (a) 12 plies of T700 carbon fibre/epoxy unidirectional prepreg (VTM 264), and (b) 10 plies of T700 carbon fibre/epoxy unidirectional prepreg with two plies of E-Glass fibre/epoxy prepreg (MTM57) on one surface of the substrate. Both composites laminates or adherends configurations, measuring 200 mm x 250 mm x 2.65 mm, were cured in an autoclave at 120°C for 1 hour in accordance with prepreg manufacturer's guidelines.

2.2 Specimen Configuration and Testing Methods

Double cantilever beam (DCB) samples were manufactured using the unmodified or filler-modified epoxy as the adhesive layer by casting the epoxy resin, with and without the carbon fillers, in between the carbon fibre and hybrid composite adherends. To create a pre-crack from one end of the adhesively bonded joint, a Teflon-tape about 40 mm long and 11 μm thick was placed between the adherends at equal distance from the two adherend surfaces. The thickness of the adhesive layer within the DCB specimen was 2 mm. To align the fillers, then before cure of the epoxy, an AC electric field of 30 V/mm and 10kHz was applied by using the conductive carbon fibre and hybrid fibre laminates as negative and positive electrodes, respectively. This process was conducted during the initial 1 hour period of curing. For purposes of simplicity, the specimens that were, and were not, subjected to the electric field are denoted as "aligned" and "random", respectively, to designate the condition of the carbon fillers. The DCB specimens were tested using a 10 kN Instron Universal Testing machine at a crosshead (crack opening) displacement rate of 1 mm/min according to ISO 25217 specification. The mode I fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , was calculated using the 'corrected beam theory method'. In measuring the through-the-thickness electrical conductivity, the composite adherends were removed from the epoxy composite [25]. The through-the-thickness DC electrical conductivity of the epoxy composite samples was measured using 34465A digital multimeter (Keysight Technologies) in accordance with ASTM D257.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Multi-scale electric field alignment of carbon fillers

CNFs and SCFs were dispersed using a three roll mill calendaring process and were shown to be randomly oriented within the epoxy (as shown in **Fig. 1a**, **1c** and **1e**). The responses of the CNFs and SCFs to the AC electric field within the epoxy resin were observed via optical microscopy. Within four minutes of applying the electric field, it was observed that the CNFs and SCFs would rotate and align along the direction of the field. **Fig. 1b**, **1d** and **1f** present optical microscope images of the SCFs and CNFs in the epoxy after four minutes of electric field exposure. Due to the differences in the dielectric properties and electrical conductivity between the fibrous fillers and the liquid medium (epoxy), the SCFs and CNFs are polarised when subject to an electric field. Also, the shape anisotropy of the fillers further induces a torque; driving the SCFs and CNFs to rotate towards the direction of the electric field.

As shown in **Fig. 1b** and **1d**, the onset of chain-like networks of the SCFs and CNFs in the epoxy resin occurred. The opposite charges at the ends of the SCFs and CNFs during application of the electric field resulted in the adjacent fibres being attracted to each other. **Fig. 1f** shows an example of simultaneous alignment of the SCFs and CNFs in the epoxy resin. The agglomeration of the CNFs towards the ends of the SCF shown on **Fig. 1f** is evidence of localised charging at the ends of the fibre [15,21-26]. However, it is interesting to note a form of *in-situ* deposition of CNFs on to the SCF. This is attributed due to a surface charge being induced along the length of the SCF [25-26]; resulting in the charged CNFs migrating and being deposited over the SCF substrate shown in **Fig. 1f**.

Figure 1: Optical micrographs of the epoxy composites with (a) randomly oriented SCFs, (b) aligned SCFs, (c) randomly oriented CNFs, (d) aligned CNFs, (e) randomly oriented SCF and CNFs, and (f) aligned SCF and CNFs. Note: the z-axis indicated the direction of the electric field being applied and the weight fractions of the SCF and CNF was 0.1%.

3.2 Electrical conductivity studies

Fig. 2a presents the effects of electric field alignment on the DC electrical conductivity of the unmodified epoxy and its composites containing SCF and/or CNF reinforcements. The electrical conductivity was measured in the through-thickness direction, which is the direction of electric field alignment. With increasing content of the random SCFs from 0.5wt% to 1.0wt%, the electrical conductivity was increased by nine and ten orders of magnitude, respectively, compared to the unmodified epoxy. The addition of randomly oriented 1.0wt% CNF resulted in an improvement of nine orders of magnitude. In a comparison between the nano- and micron-scale reinforcements at the same weight concentration (1 wt%) the SCFs provided a greater increase in the electrical conductivity than the CNFs. This was due to the longer length of the SCFs (720 μm) compared to the CNFs (135 μm), which increased the probability of fibres being in contact with adjacent fibres resulting in the increased density of conductive pathways for the electrons [15].

As shown in **Fig.2b**, the composites with the aligned SCFs and CNFs, either when used separately or together, exhibited a consistently higher DC electrical conductivity compared to their random counterparts. For instance, the epoxy composites containing 0.5wt% of aligned SCFs had an electrical conductivity that was one order of magnitude higher than the corresponding composite containing randomly oriented SCFs.

Figure 2: (a) Logarithmic plot of DC electrical conductivity of the epoxy composites containing various combinations of SCF and CNF content for both the random and aligned conditions. (b) Magnified inset of **Fig. 2a**.

Presented in Table 1 are the results that demonstrate that aligning both SCFs and CNFs increases the electrical conductivity of the epoxy more effectively than when they are randomly oriented. This is due to the end-to-end chaining and tethering of the neighbouring nano- and micron-scale fillers when subjected to an external electric field; thus, increasing the formation of conductive carbon paths for the electrons [15, 26].

Fillers	DC Electrical Conductivity (S/m)	Improvement (%)	DC Electrical Conductivity (S/m)	Improvement (%)
	Random	Random	Aligned	Aligned
Unmodified	1.1x10 ⁻¹³ (±0.2 x10 ⁻¹³)	-	-	-
0.5wt% SCF	3.1x10 ⁻⁴ (±0.3 x10 ⁻⁴)	2.5 x10 ¹²	3.9x10 ⁻³ (±0.1 x10 ⁻³)	3.5 x10 ¹³
1.0wt% SCF	6.5x10 ⁻³ (±0.4 x10 ⁻³)	5.9 x10 ¹³	1.8x10 ⁻² (±0.1 x10 ⁻²)	1.5x10 ¹⁴
1.0wt% CNF	6.0x10 ⁻⁴ (±0.1 x10 ⁻⁴)	5.4 x10 ¹²	2.0x10 ⁻³ (±0.4 x10 ⁻³)	1.8 x10 ¹³
0.5wt% SCF+1.0wt% CNF	2.6x10 ⁻³ (±0.6 x10 ⁻³)	2.4 x10 ¹³	6.8x10 ⁻³ (±0.3 x10 ⁻³)	6.1 x10 ¹³
1.0wt% SCF+1.0wt% CNF	7.4x10 ⁻³ (±0.5 x10 ⁻³)	6.7 x10 ¹³	1.9x10 ⁻² (±0.2 x10 ⁻²)	1.7 x10 ¹⁴

Table 1: Effect of nano- and micron-scale reinforcement and their orientation on the DC electrical conductivity of the epoxy composites.

3.3 Fracture toughness and fractography studies

Fig. 3 presents the mode I fracture toughness values, G_{Ic} , of the epoxy composites with different content and combinations of randomly orientated and aligned SCFs and CNFs. The unmodified epoxy had an average G_{Ic} value of 134 J/m². With the addition of randomly-orientated of 1.0wt% SCFs or 1.0wt% CNFs, there was an increase in the G_{Ic} to 715 and 1240 J/m², respectively. However, for the epoxy containing both the randomly-orientated 1.0wt.% SCFs and 1.0wt% CNFs, an additive improvement was observed, with a G_{Ic} value of 1840J/m². This is a nearly an 11-fold improvement in the fracture toughness compared to the unmodified epoxy.

Figure 3: Mode I fracture toughness of the epoxy composites containing various combinations of SCF and CNF content in the random or aligned state.

The application of an electric field further enhanced the fracture toughness of the epoxy composites containing the multi-scale carbon fillers. For instance, the epoxy composite containing the aligned 0.5wt.% and 1.0wt.% SCFs exhibited a 24% and 30% improvement, respectively, compared to corresponding randomly orientated SCFs. The epoxy composite containing the aligned 1.0wt% CNFs, had a 27% higher toughness (from 1240J/m² to 1640J/m²) compared to the composite containing randomly orientated CNFs. This level of improvement was also reported in previous findings by Ladani et al. [15,23] and Wu et al. [22] for the addition of CNFs and GNPs in epoxy, respectively. The epoxy composite containing both the aligned 1.0wt% SCFs and 1.0wt% CNFs had a G_{Ic} value of ~2550J/m², with the improvement being 38% greater than the composite containing the randomly orientated multi-scale carbon reinforcements. However, at 1.0wt% SCFs and 1.0wt% CNFs, the fracture energy was only 3% greater than the sum of toughening contributions provided by the aligned 1.0wt% SCF and 1.0wt% CNFs when used separately.

The increase to the fracture toughness of the epoxy composites is attributed to the toughening mechanisms induced by the multi-scale reinforcements. As shown in **Fig. 4a,b and c**, the scanning electron micrograph (SEM) images of the epoxy fracture surface around the crack tip revealed evidence of SCFs and CNFs that had undergone fracture and interfacial debonding from the epoxy/SCF or epoxy/CNF interface. Previous studies indicate fracture toughening is due to elastic deformation of the SCF and CNF fillers and their progressive interfacial debonding from the epoxy before rupture [15,27,28]. These toughening processes operate at near and ahead of the tip (i.e.

intrinsic toughening) during mode I crack loading. In addition, plastic void growth of the epoxy matrix surrounding the CNFs occurred, as shown in **Fig. 4c**. Previous experimental and modelling studies have revealed that void growth in the epoxy has a significant toughening effect [15,23,29]. During mode I loading, a triaxial stress field exists ahead of the crack tip causing the nanofiller to debond from the epoxy which then leads to void formation. This induces crack tip plasticity as the void grows under increasing crack opening displacement and further dissipates strain energy during the fracture process resulting in the increase in the fracture toughness of the epoxy composite [29].

Other dominant toughening mechanisms include SCF and CNF pull-out, shown respectively in **Fig. 4b** and **d**. This extrinsic toughening mechanism, that operates behind the crack tip, is due to the frictional work in the pull-out of the fillers from the matrix [15,27]. A greater amount of pull-out was observed on the fracture surface of the epoxy composite containing the aligned SCFs, CNFs and SCFs + CNFs reinforcements compared to their random counterpart. This increases the fracture toughness of the composites containing the aligned fillers, thereby increasing volume content of fibres bridging and encountering the crack wake. The present work demonstrates that extraordinarily high toughening efficiency was achieved by electric-field alignment of the carbon fibre reinforcements at multiple length and diameter scales.

Figure 4: SEM micrograph images of the modified epoxy composite fracture surface around the crack initiation region; SCF/epoxy composites in the (a) random and (b) aligned conditions; CNF/epoxy nanocomposites in the (c) random and (d) aligned conditions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Epoxy polymer composites containing aligned SCFs and CNFs were produced by using an external direct current electric field applied before curing of the epoxy matrix. The majority of the carbon nano- and micron-sized fillers, which are initially randomly orientated, were aligned along the external field direction. In addition, *in-situ* deposition of the nanofiller on to the micron-scale reinforcement occurred. From this study, it was found that the SCF reinforced epoxy composite were much more electrically conductive than the composite containing the CNFs. The alignment and combination of the carbon nano- and micron-scale fillers significantly increased both the electrical conductivity and fracture toughness of the epoxy. The toughening mechanisms provided by the nano- and micron-diameter scale were similar in nature; with the addition of the CNF promoting epoxy void growth. This study demonstrates that carbon fillers at varying length and diameter scales can be manipulated using an external electric field to achieve high levels of alignment resulting in multi-functional and hierarchically reinforced polymer composites.

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